

Online IFRA for Identification of Power Transformer Faults Based on Pulse Compression Method

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Abstract—The most accurate method, recommended for the energy transformers diagnostic, is the Frequency Response Analysis (FRA), in the form of two implementations, Impulse-Frequency Response Analysis (IFRA), and Sweep-Frequency Response Analysis (SFRA). Both implementations have their own advantages, as well as difficulties, when applied to a transformer without disconnecting them from the load. Till now, there is no clear consensus which of them is better. However, for the case of the IFRA method applied to distribution transformers, difficulties about signal injection on low voltage side can be easily overcome if the pulse compression method is used for generation of testing excitations. Using pulse compression method, other obstacles connected to high voltage application is avoided, and many signal processing advantages that exist in various system identification methods can be implemented. On that way on-line IFRA can be method of choice for preventive diagnostic of distribution transformers.

Keywords - Power transformer, on-line diagnostic, winding deformation, frequency response analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

All transformers in power system are influenced to actions of different disturbances which can cause a several types of damage. One of the most important hazards in power transformers is mechanical defect in transformer windings. That defect can occur due to lack of appropriate transportation from the factory, explosions of combustible gas in transformer oil, earthquakes, electrodynamic forces caused by external electrical faults (such is short circuit fault), etc. Multiple stresses leads to accumulated deformations of transformation

windings, insulation, or other vital parts, and finally to transformer failure, followed by withdrawal from exploitation and high follow-up costs.

In order to prevent and reduce negative consequences caused by power transformer failures, many diagnostic techniques are developed and standardized [1]-[5]. One of them, Frequency Response Analysis (FRA), is considered as a most powerful and accurate tool for sufficient winding deformation detection [1], [6]-[9]. Since the FRA considers a power transformer as a multi-input multi-output linear electric network, essence of the method is based on system identification theory [8], with specific details related only to hardware issues. Consequently, there are many particular FRA implementations, based on different hardware setups, different signal processing algorithms, with different performances under different conditions [1], [6]-[9].

In our paper, we suggest modification of IFRA method, directly applicable to distribution transformers. Particularly, we focus on excitation signal construction and some aspects of signal processing in analog and digital domain. We support some our claims by theoretical analysis and simulations, while experimental results are expected in near future.

II. FRA IN TRANSFORMER DIAGNOSTIC

Generally, any FRA implementation consists of 3 stages [9], [10], Fig 1. State 1 consists of a hardware that generates injection signal, and performs measurements of the response [9], [10]. Second and third stages deal with data storage, processing and interpretation.

Figure 1. FRA test stages [10]

Despite great number of technical papers addressing third stage, it must be highlighted that not a single aspect of its implementation can be an issue. According to current state of information technology, A/D conversion hardware with sampling rates in order of tens mega samples per second are broadly available, high speed memories of GB capacity are at every step of life, and high throughput communication links, like 4G or 5G, makes cloud processing of practically any amount of data affordable to any Internet-connected edge device. Thus only critical part of FRA equipment is hardware from stage 1, responsible for:

- injection of appropriate excitation signal in order to ensure responses with decent signal to noise ratio, and,
- low noise acquisition with proper resolution and dynamic range.

When the response that contain sufficient information is acquired, it can be stored to virtually unlimited memory resources, and wirelessly transferred to the cloud where can be processed by endless processing power. Data can be analyzed with any of numerous system identification tools, commercial or customized, based on some high-tech algorithms such are neural nets, fuzzy logic systems, etc, or simple but effective brute-force algorithms [13]-[15].

Depending on whether the transformer being tested is in exploitation, implementations of the method are classified into on-line FRA and off-line FRA.

A. Off-line FRA: Impulse-Frequency Response Analyses

For the case of off-line FRA there are two main approaches for excitation signal generation. One of them is based on impulse type excitation, called Impulse-Frequency Response Analyses (IFRA) [4], [6], [7], [11]-

[16]. In that case, detection of changes in the reactive resistance of the defective winding can be based on two principles:

- the analysis of transient response, arising after exposure of transformer to the excitation in the form of an electrical impulse;
- Periodic impulse train: if electrical impulses are periodic, response in time domain can be processed with some of discrete transforms, and further analysis is conducted in frequency domain.

If the excitation is in the form of low voltage impulses (1V–20V typically), then approach is also called Low-Voltage Impulse method (LVI).

B. Off-line FRA: Sweep-Frequency Response Analysis

Another approach is based on the analysis of the frequency transfer function of the windings, where result is obtained by successive supply of the sinusoidal test voltage, typically 1-20 V_{RMS}, with different frequencies. The result is the ratio of a steady sinusoidal output from a test object, subject to a steady sinusoidal input. However, testing excitation can be in the form of multi-sine, or sweep-sine signal with reach harmonic spectrum. In practice, the approach is called Sweep-Frequency Response Analysis (SFRA) [5]-[7], [12].

C. Off-line SFRA and IFRA relation

In essence, both approaches are very close, and differ only in the type of excitation. Detection of winding violations of in these methods is made by comparison of actual frequency or transient response on phases (defectogram), concerning each other, or concerning the basic responses registered on the transformer earlier (normogram) in a faultless state.

D. On-line FRA

Off-line FRA implementations yield very accurate results, but assume transformer disconnection from the power grid and loads, and leave consumers without electricity. On the other hand, on-line FRA implementation, with target transformer in service, is an attractive alternative, allowing transformer monitoring at any time, even continuously [6],[7],[9],[10],[17]-[19].

Since on-line FRA is only specific type of FRA it fits into same 3 stages from Fig 1. The main differences compared to off-line FRA are implementation of stage 1. There are several problems in the realization of the step 1 [6], [7], [9], [10], [17]-[19]; the main of them are following:

- The measurement is performed under high voltages present in the system, so the interface to measurement equipment must be properly isolated.
- The power grid and loads are part of the system, and the response to the excitation is response of the complete system, not only target transformer. Effects of external voltages and noise sources are also included.
- Because of time varying power line voltage, and also time varying current amplitudes, hysteresis effects cause time wearying transformer reactance. This leads to different responses for the same healthy transformer.

There is extensive quantity of technical and scientific papers that suggest various solutions to mentioned problems. Most of them are based on IFRA implementation, where uncontrolled high voltage impulses, similar to lighting, are applied as excitation, and bushing tap couplers are used as an access point for measurement. There are also suggestions that commutation of power factor correction switches can be used as transformer excitation. In both cases, current transformers based on Rogowski coil can be used for current measurement.

There are also few reports that suggest application of SFRA method, but with serious drawbacks related to signal injection.

III. ON-LINE IFRA FOR DISTRIBUTION TRANSFORMERS

For a 10kV/0.4kV distribution transformer, simplified grid connection with consumer loads, together with LV load Z_p , and grid MV generator V_g , is presented on Fig. 2.

Consequently, are two options about IFRA excitation: it can be applied on MV side (port A), or on LV side (port B).

Figure 2. Simplified grid connection of 10kV/0.4kV distribution transformer

A. Excitation on primary side, port A

Since the grid impedance Z_g , is significantly lower than equivalent input impedance at the primary (MV) side of the transformer, it is questionable what portion of excitation current enters primary winding, and certainly a great part of excitation energy flows into the grid towards V_g . There is an option for signal injection, which is not mentioned in observed FRA literature, based on grid impedance measurement experiences, for example [20], but directly applicable only to small fraction of useful frequencies. Additionally, delta-connected primary windings requires differential excitation what further complicates implementation.

B. Excitation on secondary side, port B

Secondary (LV) side of the distribution transformer offers much more flexibility for connection of the excitation generator, due to lower voltage and more accessible terminals. Impedance seen in the secondary port of the transformer is much lower than impedance of the consumer loads, so the most of the excitation energy would enter transformer network. Connection is simpler, since wye configuration of the secondary windings allows single-ended excitation. On the other hand, excitation source requires much more current capacity, compared to source used for primary side. However, this approach has more advantages than disadvantages, and is used more frequently.

C. Measurement issues

Simplified principal diagram of measurement setup, used for measurement of equivalent impedance $Z_T(j\omega)$ presented on Fig 3. It should be noticed that $Z_T(j\omega)$ is not pure characteristic parameter of the transformer since it includes contribution of impedances connected to all other terminals.

Contribution of grid voltage and all voltages on other transformer terminals is represented as voltage generator V_{N1} , while contribution of consumer loads on LV side is represented as a current generator I_{N2} . Both

generators act as source of periodic noise with typically 50Hz fundamental frequency. Contribution of all other noise sources is represented with white noise current generator I_n . Voltage measured on point B consists of three parts:

$$V_B(j\omega) = I_T Z_T + I_n Z_T + \underbrace{V_{N1} + I_{N2} Z_T}_{V_{BN}(j\omega)} \quad (1)$$

First part, $V_T(j\omega)$ is response to the artificial excitation I_T . Second part, $V_n(j\omega)$ is the contribution of the white noise current generator I_n . It can be efficiently eliminated using well known noise mitigation techniques, based on extensive averaging, proper frequency bandwidth partitioning, and advanced filtration. Third part, $V_{BN}(j\omega)$ is contribution of periodic noise sources V_{N1} and I_{N2} . Theoretically, this part can be estimated by measurement with $I_T = 0$, together with random noise elimination techniques:

$$V_{BN}(j\omega) = V_B(j\omega, I_T = 0, I_n = 0). \quad (1)$$

Finally, the required response can be determined by formal equation:

$$V_T(j\omega) = V_B(j\omega) - \underbrace{V_{BN}(j\omega)}_{\rightarrow 0}. \quad (2)$$

The subtraction in the previous equation is not a mathematical operation, but rather a procedure for eliminating the contribution of $V_{BN}(j\omega)$. Usually, V_{BN} contribution to V_T is insertion of fundamental and several even harmonics, and usually its impact is present for frequencies below 1kHz. In that case, subtraction from the previous equation is performed by proper filtration in time domain. In rare, more complicated cases, additional countermeasures should be preformed.

IV. GENERATION OF EXCITATION SIGNAL

The best results for linear system identification in frequency domain is achieved by using sweep signal as excitation, and signal processing techniques developed for network analyzers. Such principle is applied in SFRA. But serious practical issue in all on-line FRA is interfacing of linear signal generator to power grid, and long lasting procedure. The alternative option is to design excitation signal in the form of narrow high amplitude impulse, which can mimic atmospheric lighting strokes, or to design

Figure 3. Simplified principal diagram of measurement setup

excitation signal which mimic normal operation of consumer load. In both cases, power system stays in normal operation condition.

A. Excitation signal in impulse form

Excitation signal in impulse form is basis of almost all IFRA methods. If signal is controllably generated by means of power electronic devices, it can be in rectangular form:

$$x(t) = A \cdot w \cdot \text{rect}(w \cdot t). \quad (3)$$

$x(t)$ can be current or voltage, where w is width of the impulse, and Aw is impulse amplitude. If $A=1$ and $w \rightarrow \infty$, then $x(t)$ approaches Dirac Delta impulse, $x(t) \rightarrow \delta(t)$. In that case, response to $x(t)$ is impulse response, and Fourier transform of that response is required frequency response. In practice, such a case is far from true, since w and Aw are limited by safety and implementation reasons. For the practical $x(t)$, its frequency spectrum is in the form:

$$X(j\omega) = F_T\{x(t)\} = A \cdot \text{sinc}(\omega / 2w). \quad (5)$$

First null of frequency spectrum is at $\omega_{01} / 2w = 1 \Rightarrow \omega_{01} = 2w$, giving useful range for transformer network identification of approximately $3/4$ of the $(0, \omega_{01})$ interval,

Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Amplitude spectrum of rectangular impulse

For the purpose of white noise elimination, extensive averaging should be implemented, and excitation signal should be periodic, and synchronized to line frequency (50Hz/60Hz). The train of excitation impulses should be accomplished by repetition period $T_0=2\pi/\omega_0$, giving discrete spectrum:

$$X[k] = \frac{1}{T} X(j \cdot (\omega = k\omega_0)), k \in \mathbf{Z} \quad (4)$$

Applying such a signal as an excitation I_T from Fig. 3, and if noise sources are eliminated by proper signal processing techniques, discrete version of equivalent impedance (or admittance) can be estimated in the form:

$$Z_T[k] = 1/Y_T[k] = V_T[k]/X[k]. \quad (5)$$

B. Excitation signal in compressed impulse form

Narrow and high amplitude impulses are difficult to control. Reduction of the signal amplitude and expanding of the signal width is not a good option, since this approach leads to narrowing the excitation signal spectrum, decrease in signal power, and consequently to weak SNR. In order to overcome disadvantages of the impulse excitation in time domain, while keeping good characteristics in frequency domain, different pulse compression techniques can be applied [21], with a utilization of Maximum Length Binary Sequences (MLBS) as a most common [22]-[24].

Contrary to impulse shape, MLBS is the periodic sequence with two discrete amplitude levels, $\{0, X_0\}$, or $\{-X_0/2, +X_0/2\}$. Generation of the sequence is easily accomplished by means of circular shift register with proper feedback. The generated binary sequence is N periodic with repetition period T_0 , giving the same amplitude spectra as rectangular impulse:

$$|X[k]| = \underbrace{\left(\frac{X_0 \sqrt{N+1}}{2N} \right)}_A \operatorname{sinc}\left(\frac{k}{N}\right), k \neq 0, \quad (6)$$

where $N = 2^n - 1$ is the signal period, and n is a length of the shift register. The clock of the shift register $t_{clk}=2\pi/\omega_{clk}$ is related to the signal period in the form $T_0=2\pi/\omega_0=N \cdot t_{clk}$.

Figure 5. Amplitude spectrum of the MLBS excitation

Portion of the amplitude spectra (continual approximation) of the signal $X[k]$ is depicted on Fig. 5.

We defined useful part of the spectrum (~ 10 dB reduction in harmonics amplitude) in the range $\omega < \sim 0.75 \omega_{clk}$, so the high-order low-pass filter with $\sim 0.75 \omega_{clk}$ cut-off frequency is applied later. However some other ranges can be used.

C. Proposal of the injection of the excitation signal

According to switching nature of the proposed excitation signal, and switching frequencies below 5MHz, signal injection can be accomplished using high-speed bilateral solid-state switch, Fig. 6, based on appropriate high-speed MOS transistor [25], for example APT6038BLL. Gate driver of the transistor M is driven by MLBS generator. When transistor is turned ON, voltage on B' port is ~ 0 V. When transistor is turned off, voltage on B' port is equal to LV line voltage. On that way, voltage on port B' is modulated MLSB sequence:

$$v_{B'}(t) = x(t) \cdot 230\sqrt{2} \cos(\omega_L t), \omega_L = 100\pi, \quad (7)$$

Figure 6. High speed bilateral solid-state switch.

where ω_L is power line frequency. Modulation of $x(t)$, with 50Hz cosine-wave, slightly changes original spectrum:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} V_B(j\omega) &= \frac{X(j\omega + j\omega_L) + X(j\omega - j\omega_L)}{2} \\ V_B(j\omega) &\approx X(j\omega) \end{aligned} \right\} (10)$$

what have negligible influence if synchronization between ω_0 and ω_L is achieved.

Using injection circuit from Fig. 6, the resulting equivalent voltage generator at port B' have the same reach spectrum as displayed in Fig. 5.

V. MEASUREMENT PROPOSAL AND SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Transformer model

For the simulation purposes, simplified RLC equivalent circuit (single phase) of a distribution transformer is assumed (Fig. 7) [26], [27]. The meaning of the components in the model: $C_{S1,2}$ – serial capacitances, $R_{S1,2}$ – ohmic resistances $L_{S1,2}$ – leakage inductances, and $C_{g1,2}$ – parallel capacitances against copper/core in primary and secondary windings; L_m and R_m are magnetization inductance and magnetic core losses; C_{12} – mutual capacitive coupling between MV and LV windings. Primary of the transformer is terminated with grid impedance with typical value of 300Ω. Example of the theoretical equivalent LV admittance $Y_T = 1/Z_T$, of the assumed transformer is given in Fig 8. At low frequencies, below 1 kHz the magnetizing inductance is dominant. The first two parallel resonance frequency picks, at ~3kHz and ~10kHz originate from the anti-resonance between the magnetizing inductance L_m and parallel capacitances $C_{g1,2}$. The following resonance at ~20kHz is due to serial connection of leakage inductances and $C_{g1,2}$.

Figure 7. Transformer model, single phase, used for simulation

The third anti-resonance is caused by influence of parallel capacitances and leakage inductances. At higher frequencies, typically below 1MHz, the winding capacitances and inductances have dominant influence. Any mechanical change within the winding structure would affect this frequency range.

At frequencies of couple of MHz and beyond, several side effects have significant impact, and measurement results are unusable [26][27].

For the simulation purposes, measurement setup is made according to Fig. 6. Bilateral switch is implemented using universal Spice semiconductor models. Resistor R_x from Fig. 6. is set to 60Ω, what limits maximal injection current to ~5A, what is acceptable for transistor intended for the future real experiments. For the MLBS generator 12-bit shift register is used. Clock period T_{clk} is set to 0.6105μs, and together with $N = 4095$ provides $T_0 = 2.5$ ms and synchronism to 50Hz. Current and voltage generators V_{N1} and I_{N2} are defined as a slightly clipped sine wave signals with net effect of 50Hz/230V_{RMS} at port B. On that way even harmonic content is provided. White noise source I_n is not implemented, since in practice proper countermeasures efficiently suppress its influence [26].

Figure 8. typical LV admittance with reference to the parameters of the equivalent circuit from Fig 7.

Current I_T (through R_x) and voltage V_B are measured and processed with 50Hz notch filter in series with first order high-pass filter with 200Hz cut-off frequency, as well as anti-aliasing sixth order low-pass filter with 1MHz cut-off frequency. Acquisition of the response is started one T_0 period after start of excitation, on order to avoid transient regime. Response signals are acquired with 4MHz sampling rate, and FFT is performed over single T_0 period. Without any further processing, required admittance is calculated using (7), and result is depicted on Fig 9. The unsatisfactory result is achieved due to spectra leaking caused by V_{N1} and I_{N2} interference (higher harmonics).

Figure 9. Calculated admittance by using (7), without post-processing.

By increasing high-pass filter to order of two, and by averaging 64 T_0 sampled intervals, significantly better result is achieved (Fig. 10). It can be seen that estimated admittance, in the 1kHz – 1MHz range is in good agreement with calculated admittance, even with simple data post processing.

Figure 10. Calculated admittance by using (7), with post-processing

VI. CONCLUSION

According to simulations, proposed excitation signal in the form of MLBS, can be efficiently generated and injected in power lines on LV side of distribution transformer, without unnatural stress of the system. Since MLBS signal has identical spectral characteristics as high amplitude and narrow width rectangular impulse, it is suitable for identification of transformer frequency characteristics. As in all frequency domain system identification implementations, synchronization and averaging are mandatory. Even with simple post processing of the acquired response, results are promising.

Important aspect of the demonstrated measurement is a dynamic range of the response, in our example it is ~ 80 dB, what can be covered by 16 bit AD conversion. However, required dynamic range in practice is 120dB [26], so the standard measures for greater dynamic range should be implemented in real implementation of the proposed method. Of

course, final conclusion can be conducted after real hardware testing in real environment.

Proposed method, in the form described in our paper, is suitable for LV side of distribution transformers, due to breakdown voltages of semiconductor switches. With proper modifications, by using HF transformers for example, it is possible to adapt proposed method for MV side of transformer. However, principal obstacles related to excitation on MV side of transformer stays, no matter of excitation method.

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